

Pheripheral Ossifying fibroma – A case report

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ABSTRACT:

Localized gingival overgrowth mostly frequently occurred lesions in the oral cavity; there are few histological types of focal overgrowth occur on the gingiva, such as the peripheral giant cell granuloma, the giant cell fibroma, the pyogenic granuloma, peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF). Among most of the lesions; infrequently occurring gingival lesion is the POF. A case presentation of 29- year male with the gingival overgrowth in the maxillary left incisor region. Clinically, the lesion was asymptomatic, well demarcated focal mass of tissue on the gingiva, with a sessile or pedunculated base. It is pale pink, slightly reddened in appearance. Surgical excision of the lesion was done followed by histopathological confirmation. The recurrence rate for POF is 20%; close post-operative follow-up is required.

INTRODUCTION:

Localized gingival overgrowth frequently occurred in the oral cavity; Peripheral ossifying fibroma (POF) are commonly of them. It is most commonly occurring gingival lesion; characterised by highly vascular, cementum - like growth material and rarely having dystrophic calcification.¹

POF was described as a reactive type of gingival lesion in 1972. The etiological causes include trauma, local elements like presence of calculus and plaque, and impingement by dental appliances or restorations.² The size of the lesion usually ranges between ≥ 2 cm but larger lesions have also been found which can lead to notable teeth displacement, lip incompetence and may even lead to changes in facial proportions.

The color varies from pink to red, and in few cases, tooth displacement has also been reported accompanying with interdental bone loss³.

It accounts 3.1% of oral tumor and 9.6% of gingival lesion². It is suggested that 50% of lesion occurred between 5 and 25 years of age and peak at 13 years, while the mean age was 29 years³. Female prediction varies from 2:1 to 3:2³. The lesion are equally distributed between the maxilla and mandible; and 80% of the lesions occurred anterior to the molar area³.

Histologically, it is composed of a gingival overgrowth comprising islands; trabeculae of woven and lamellar bone in a cellular fibrous connective tissue stroma¹. Chronic inflammatory cells have also been found in the periphery of the lesion.

Following are the two theories that have been reported to find out the etiological characteristics of the lesion⁵.

1. According to the first theory POF initially presents itself as pyogenic granuloma which later on undergoes calcification.
2. According to the second hypothesis, an inflammatory hyperplasia in the periodontal ligament cells is the cause of the lesion. (This theory is more widely recognised)

Additionally, there is proof that calcified matrix-rich oxytalan fibers remains present in the Peripheral ossifying fibroma.⁶

CASE REPORT:

A male patient aged 29 came with a chief complain of painless growth on the gingival margin in the upper left front region of the teeth, which started as a small painless lesion last 5 months and showed a gradual increase in size. There was no relevant history of pain and bleeding, and no relevant medical history was obtained at the time of treatment.

On Intraoral examination lesion was approximately 1.0cm X 0.8cm in size in 10% formalin firm, sessile, slightly reddened in appearance and pale pinkish in colour which is located on the gingival margin with respect to maxillary left incisor region (figure 1 & 2).The lesion extends from distal aspect of left central incisor to that of lateral incisor. Bone loss was noticed radiographically with respect to maxillary left central and lateral incisor (figure3).

The differential diagnosis suggests of pyogenic granuloma and peripheral ossifying fibroma. On the basis of clinical and radiographic findings; the provisional diagnosis was Pyogenic granuloma.

Both non-surgical and surgical line of treatment were recommended. Nonsurgical periodontal therapy were performed for removal of local etiological factors. After 1 week of oral prophylaxis re-evaluation; surgical excision was performed, and periodontal dressings were placed (figure 4 & 6). Postoperative instructions were given, and antibiotics and analgesics were prescribed (i.e cap Amoxicillin 500 mg tds for three days; tab zerodol sp b.d for three days) and oral rinses (0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate twice a day for 15 days). Patient was recalled after one week for removal of periodontal dressings. The excised tissue was placed in 10% formalin and sent for further histopathological analysis (figure 5).

Histopathological examination with H & E-stained section reveals of stratified squamous epithelial. The underlying connective tissue stream shows pulp fibroblasts inflammatory cells, blood vessels cells, collagen fibers & ossifications (figure 8 & 9).

Overall, histopathological examination suggests of **Peripheral Ossifying Fibroma**.

Fig 1&2: - Clinical photographs of lesion with 21, 22

Fig 3: - Radiographs shows bone loss in Maxillary Anterior region.

Fig 4: - Immediate after excision

Fig 5: - Clinical picture of excised lesion

Fig 6: - Pictures showing COE pack placement.

Fig 7: -post operative photographs after 10 days

Fig 8 & 9: - Histopathological (H&E) Stained sections at 10x and 40x shows Connective tissue stroma with proliferating fibroblasts.

DISCUSSION:

Menzel originally provided a clinical description of the lesion known as a "ossifying fibroma" in 1972, and Montgomery coined the word in 1927⁸. Eversole and Rovin earlier noted that POFs exhibit a variable histologic response to irritation in comparison with pyogenic granuloma and peripheral giant cell granuloma, which depicts same sex, site predilection and clinical presentation⁵.

According to **Kfir et al.**, POF normally has a diameter of less than 1.5 cm, although there have also been reports of gigantic POFs up to 9 cm in diameter⁹.

The prevalence of POF is generally higher in females during the 2nd decade of life due to hormonal effect, particularly of oestrogen and progesterone.

POF is common in females than in males because of the variations in hormonal levels during puberty and pregnancy.

Generally oral lesions have the same clinical presentation, that's why it is challenging to diagnose POF solely on the basis of its clinical relevance.

Pyogenic granuloma, peripheral fibroma, POF, and peripheral giant cell granuloma are all possible diagnosis for POF¹⁰. Therefore, the diagnosis of peripheral ossifying fibroma is based not only on the clinical signs but also by the radiographic and histopathologic findings¹.

The microscopic array of the POF is characterized by the presence of fibrous proliferation which is related with the presence of mineralized components.

The percentage of mineralized components ranges from 23 to 75. Peripheral ossifying fibroma has three different sorts of components, according to **Butcher and Hansen**¹¹. These are: -

1. Dystrophic calcifications
2. Bone (woven/lamellar)
3. Cementum.

Behaviour of peripheral ossifying fibroma shows higher recurrence rate. **Cundiff** noted a 16% recurrence rate, while **Eversole and Robin's** study of a series revealed a 20% recurrence rate of the POF¹². Additionally, **Mesquita et al.** discovered that there was more argyrophilic nucleolar organiser region and proliferating cell nuclear antigen positive cells in POF, indicating that the lesion was highly proliferative, which affected the treatment options.

CONCLUSION:

For confirming the diagnosis of POF, a histopathological study is required along with the detailed clinical and radiographic findings because there are several other gingival reactive lesions like PGCG, pyogenic granuloma, and irritant fibroma which have similar clinical presentations and also share the same etiological factors such as trauma, presence of plaque and calculus, irritation caused due to a dental appliance or over hanging restoration etc. Due to this reason it's critical to have a thorough understanding of the challenging diagnosis of these particular lesions in order to reach a proper conclusion so that appropriate necessary treatment can be provided to the patient.

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